

A scalable deep learning framework for daily precipitation downscaling: architecture, accuracy, and adaptability

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ABSTRACT

Global climate models provide essential large-scale climate projections, yet their coarse spatial resolution (0.5°–4°) limits understanding of urbanization's impact on regional climate dynamics. This study presents the Deep Residual Network for Precipitation Downscaling (DRN-PD), a modular neural architecture designed to enhance spatial precision and modeling interpretability in daily precipitation downscaling. By integrating CMIP6 atmospheric predictors, high-resolution land use data, and CHIRPS observations, DRN-PD advances understanding of climate–land surface interactions. Applied to the Yangtze Delta Megalopolis, the model achieves 18-fold spatial refinement, generating precipitation outputs at 5 km resolution. It consistently reproduces seasonal precipitation patterns, with mean absolute errors of 2.81–7.28 mm and root mean square errors below 11.28 mm. Spatial evaluations show strong agreement with observed rainfall distributions, achieving cosine similarity values exceeding 0.914 and effectively capturing rainfall centers and gradients. Incorporating a data augmentation strategy emphasizing extreme rainfall events, the model improves accuracy in high-intensity rainfall zones, with reduced relative errors and enhanced cosine similarity. These results demonstrate that DRN-PD, combined with appropriate training strategies, can effectively capture precipitation patterns across varying climatic and geographic contexts. This research contributes a practical tool for exploring climate–environment dynamics and supports evidence-based decision-making under increasing climate variability.

Key words: climate change, convolutional neural network, deep learning, land use, precipitation downscaling, Yangtze Delta Megalopolis

HIGHLIGHTS

- A modular deep residual network (DRN-PD) integrates CMIP6, land use, and CHIRPS data to achieve 18× spatial refinement in daily precipitation downscaling.
- Applied to the Yangtze Delta Megalopolis, the model achieves robust seasonal accuracy, effectively capturing rainfall centers and spatial gradients.
- The adaptive architecture enables scalable deployment with improved performance under heavy rainfall conditions.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

INTRODUCTION

Climate change and urbanization have emerged as dominant forces reshaping regional hydrological systems (Zhang *et al.* 2022). Accelerating greenhouse gas emissions have indeed disrupted the exchange of moisture and heat between the land surface and atmosphere, contributing to increased rainfall uncertainty and the rising frequency of extreme weather events, such as concentrated precipitation and urban floods (IPCC 2021). In high-density urban agglomerations, large-scale urban development and land-use transformation amplify these challenges, significantly altering hydrological processes and intensifying localized precipitation dynamics (Liu *et al.* 2022; Song *et al.* 2024). As a result, these regions face severe climate-related vulnerabilities, underscoring the critical importance of high-resolution precipitation data for understanding regional hydrological variability, mitigating flood risks, and ensuring resilient urban infrastructure (Stevens & Bony 2013; Gudmundsson *et al.* 2021).

Global climate models (GCMs) play a pivotal role in large-scale climate projections, simulating atmospheric circulation under diverse forcing scenarios (Cao *et al.* 2019; Wu *et al.* 2019). However, their coarse spatial resolution (typically 0.5°–4°) restricts their applicability for regional or urban-scale analyses, where fine-scale spatial variability in precipitation is essential (Vandal *et al.* 2019). Downscaling techniques address this limitation by refining GCM outputs, bridging global-scale dynamics with localized requirements (Vaittinada Ayar *et al.* 2016; Vandal 2018). Dynamical downscaling, which nests regional climate models within GCMs, enhances simulation reliability but it is contingent upon explicit physical mechanisms and considerable computational resources (Dong *et al.* 2021; Trinh-Tuan *et al.* 2025). Statistical downscaling, in contrast, employs empirical and/or statistical relationships between large-scale predictors (e.g., geopotential height, wind fields, humidity) and regional climate variables (e.g., precipitation, temperature) to improve spatial resolution (Sunyer *et al.* 2012; Tang *et al.* 2016). Machine learning and deep learning approaches have emerged as flexible and computationally efficient alternatives, capable of capturing complex patterns and non-linear interactions in climate systems (Tang *et al.* 2016; Zhang *et al.* 2018). However, current deep learning frameworks often focus solely on reconstructing coarse-resolution rainfall using super-resolution techniques (Vandal *et al.* 2019; F. Wang *et al.* 2023; Bhakare *et al.* 2025) or modeling direct relationships between meteorological drivers and precipitation (Nasseri *et al.* 2013; Sun & Lan 2021; Fu *et al.* 2024), neglecting the combined influence of climate change and regional land-use factors on rainfall dynamics. This gap underscores the need for innovative methods that integrate climate drivers and localized environmental factors and resolve the scale inconsistency between them to improve the accuracy and applicability of precipitation modeling.

To address these challenges, this study proposes a modular deep residual network that incorporates multiresolution input variables, including coarse-resolution meteorological drivers and high-resolution regional environmental factors, such as land use. The framework is designed to deliver high-resolution precipitation estimates tailored to flood risk management and urban planning needs, with application to highly urbanized regions. By bridging global and regional perspectives, this study advances the understanding of rainfall variability driven by the complex interplay of climate change and regional environmental transformations, offering a robust tool for hydrological modeling and urban-scale climate adaptation planning.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Deep learning approaches have gained prominence as computationally efficient alternatives to traditional downscaling techniques, capable of capturing complex spatial patterns and nonlinear interactions in climate datasets (Hsieh 2009). Some studies typically established relationships between environmental variables and precipitation at coarse resolutions, assuming these relationships would also hold at finer resolutions (Agam *et al.* 2007). High-resolution precipitation was then simulated using predictors such as digital elevation models (DEMs), vegetation indices (e.g., normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI), enhanced vegetation index, leaf area index), drought indices, land use, and geographic coordinates. Algorithms employed in these studies included gradient boosting regressors, support vector machines, stepwise linear regression, multiple linear regression, and multilayer perceptrons (Alexakis & Tsanis 2016; Yang *et al.* 2018; Elnashar *et al.* 2020; Kumar *et al.* 2025). However, these methods face notable limitations. First, regional environmental variables like DEM and vegetation indices exhibit a degree of 'inertia,' changing slowly over time, which makes them more suitable for simulating precipitation at monthly, seasonal, or annual scales. Second, these models treat each data point as an independent observation with a set of features, irrespective of its geographic location, failing to account for spatial dependencies.

Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have demonstrated superior performance in addressing these spatial dependencies. For example, Wang *et al.* (2021) combined CNNs with residual networks to construct a super-resolution deep residual

network (SRDRN) model, achieving 6×, 12×, and 24× downscaling for precipitation and temperature, with results outperforming traditional analog construction methods. Similarly, [Sha et al. \(2020\)](#) developed a Nest-UNet deep learning network for precipitation downscaling, showing that both Nest-UNet and UNet outperformed bias correction and spatial disaggregation (BCSD) methods in terms of accuracy and spatial detail. Despite these advancements, most studies using super-resolution techniques focus on reconstructing coarse-resolution rainfall datasets, limiting their physical interpretability. To cope with this limitation, [Sun & Lan \(2021\)](#) downscaled 0.7° resolution ERA-Interim data to 0.1° using CNN models and demonstrated performance improvements over generalized linear models. However, the CNN results still lagged behind those obtained using bias correction methods like BCSD. [Pan et al. \(2019\)](#) further explored CNN-based approaches by incorporating atmospheric variables such as precipitable water (PW) and geopotential height (GPH) to enhance the precision of precipitation simulations derived from dynamical models, while [González-Abad & Gutiérrez \(2025\)](#) compared CNN and UNet architectures, emphasizing the continued challenges in downscaling precipitation, particularly for extreme events. Many of these studies rely on coarse-resolution atmospheric variables as inputs, incorporating predictors such as GPH and PW to improve simulations. However, they fail to capture the combined influence of climate dynamics and urban transformations on precipitation variability. A critical challenge remains in resolving scale inconsistencies between coarse-resolution GCM outputs and high-resolution environmental predictors. Most deep learning approaches inadequately integrate dynamic interactions between climate drivers and localized land-use factors, which are essential for capturing the hydrological impacts of urbanization and regional environmental changes. Addressing these gaps necessitates innovative architectures that can seamlessly merge multiscale inputs, improve spatial and temporal precision, and deliver actionable insights for both historical climate analyses and future projections.

STUDY AREA

China's economy has grown rapidly and the level of urbanization has increased dramatically since the implementation of the reform and opening policy in 1978. The nominal gross domestic product (GDP) has increased 352 times from 367.87 billion Chinese yuan (CNY) in 1978 to 129.43 trillion CNY in 2024, while its corresponding urban population percentage has risen from 17.92 to 66.16%. The Yangtze River Delta is one of the most developed regions in China, the growth rate of whose economic and urban development is ahead of the national average ([Yu et al. 2021](#)). To strengthen the coordination and cooperation in cross-city/regional development and enhance the international competitiveness of Chinese cities, the *Development Plan for the Yangtze Delta Megalopolis* (YDM) has been issued by Chinese central government in 2016, making the development of the YDM as one of the national strategies.

The YDM, located in the downstream region of the Yangtze River Basin, covers an area of approximately 2.12×10^5 km² and includes Shanghai, 9 cities in Jiangsu Province (e.g., Nanjing, Suzhou), 8 cities in Zhejiang Province (e.g., Hangzhou, Ningbo), and 8 cities in Anhui Province (e.g., Hefei, Wuhu) ([Figure 1](#)). The region represents a microcosm of China's national growth, with economic and urban expansion surpassing national averages. This strategic cluster of cities has been pivotal in regional and cross-border development efforts. By the end of 2023, its registered population had reached 134.39 million, accounting for 9.54% of China's population and 1.65% of the world's. The nominal GDP for the same year was 25.42 trillion CNY, contributing 19.64% of China's GDP and 3.35% of the global GDP ([Figure 2](#)). Given its high urbanization, economic vitality, and dense population, the YDM is particularly vulnerable to climate change impacts. Accurate precipitation forecasts are critical for safeguarding water resources, supporting sustainable urban development, and enhancing disaster resilience in this dynamic region.

DATA AND METHODOLOGY

Predictors and predictand

Compared to station-based field observations, gridded reanalysis precipitation data offer spatial continuity and standardized formatting, making them particularly suitable for deep learning applications that produce spatially distributed outputs. In this study, the gridded reanalysis precipitation data served as the predictand, representing the target variable to be estimated through the downscaling process. Based on the criteria of extensive temporal coverage, high spatial resolution, and daily-scale data availability, the CHIRPS dataset was selected. Released in 2015 by the University of California Santa Barbara Climate Hazards Center, this dataset integrates ground station and satellite remote sensing data, offering a historical range from 1981 to the present with a spatial resolution of 5 km, fully covering the YDM ([Funk et al. 2015](#); [Harrison et al. 2022](#)).

Figure 1 | Study area of the YDM, China. Background from Terrain tiles by Stamen Design.

Figure 2 | Population and GDP of the YDM by the end of 2023.

Compared to other widely used datasets such as GPCC (0.25°, monthly), ERA5-Land (0.1°, hourly), and MERRA-2 or CFSR (0.5°, hourly), CHIRPS offers the finest spatial resolution at daily scale, which is critical for capturing localized rainfall variability. This resolution closely aligns with the World Meteorological Organization (WMO)'s recommendation of one precipitation station per 10–20 km² in urban areas (WMO 2008), making CHIRPS particularly suitable for investigating urbanization-induced rainfall changes in the YDM.

The determination of predictors is a critical step in developing precipitation downscaling models. Predictors were drawn from the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP), a global initiative comparing large-scale climate models since 1995 (Taylor *et al.* 2012). CMIP6 represents the latest phase of this project, featuring extensive climate datasets widely adopted by researchers (Eyring *et al.* 2016). This study utilized outputs from the CSM2-MR model, developed by the Beijing Climate Center (BCC) of the China Meteorological Administration, with a spatial resolution of 1.125° × 1.125° and historical coverage from 1851 to 2014 (Wu *et al.* 2019). The CSM2-MR model was selected due to its robust performance in simulating the East Asian monsoon climate and its ability to accurately capture rainfall characteristics, particularly north-south rainfall trends in China and precipitation patterns in the Yangtze River Basin (Xin *et al.* 2020; Li *et al.* 2021), aligning closely with the regional focus of this study on the YDM. Six physical variables – relative humidity (RH) and GPH at 500 and 850 hPa, sea level pressure (PSL), and near-surface air temperature (TAS) – were selected as predictors based on their established relevance to surface precipitation formation (Kunkel *et al.* 2020; Li *et al.* 2023). To align with the spatial domain of the YDM (28°N–35°N), these predictors were resampled to a resolution of 90 km × 90 km to align with the upsampling factors required by the subsequent deep learning architecture. Given the proximity between the native resolution of the CSM2-MR model (~106 km on average over the YDM) and the target resolution (90 km), the nearest neighbor interpolation was considered an acceptable and computationally efficient resampling choice.

To capture the interaction between urbanization and regional climate dynamics, this study incorporated land use factors alongside atmospheric variables. The European Space Agency Climate Change Initiative Land Cover dataset (ESA-CCI-LC) (Defourny *et al.* 2017, 2020), developed by UCLouvain, provides global land cover classification data with a horizontal resolution of 300 m and an annual temporal resolution spanning 1992 to the present. Referencing the Chinese national standards of *Current Land use Classification* (GB/T 21010-2017) and *Code for Classification of Urban Land Use and Planning Standards of Development Land* (GB 50137-2011), land cover data were converted into land use classifications, resulting in a high-resolution dataset tailored to the YDM.

In addition, the input for the neural network model consists of structured data, which is projected onto a two-dimensional Cartesian coordinate system and exhibits a rectangular shape. However, the study area, such as the YDM, has irregular boundaries. Therefore, a study area indicator variable was introduced, with values assigned as 1 for regions within the study area and 0 for regions outside of it. Table 1 provides an overview of the predictors and predictand employed in the downscaling model.

Table 1 | Predictors and predictand of the precipitation downscaling model for the YDM

	Variable	Data source	Characteristic	Temporal resolution	Temporal coverage	Vertical resolution	Preprocessing
Predictor	500 hPa RH	BCC-CSM2-MR	Physical status of the atmosphere	Daily	Available: 1851/01/01 to 2014/12/31; Used in this study: 1992/01/01 to 2014/12/31	1.125°	Resampled to 90 km
	850 hPa RH						
	500 hPa GPH						
Predictor	850 hPa GPH	ESA-CCI-LC	Underlying situation	Yearly	Available: 1992 to present; Used in this study: 1992 to 2014	300 m	Converted to land use map and resampled to 5 km
	PSL						
	TAS						
Predictor	LULC	Customized	Study area	/	/	5 km	
Predictand	Gridded precipitation	CHIRPS	Target variable	Daily	Available: 1981/01/01 to present; Used in this study: 1992/01/01 to 2014/12/31	5 km	

Modularized deep learning components

The gridded precipitation data exhibits significant spatial distribution and nonlinear characteristics. To analyze these patterns effectively, CNNs were employed to capture the spatial distribution of precipitation. Residual structures were integrated to enhance gradient propagation, thereby facilitating the training of deeper neural networks. Additionally, the rectified linear unit (ReLU) activation function was utilized to introduce nonlinearity, mitigating the vanishing gradient problem and improving computational efficiency. Furthermore, batch normalization was applied after each hidden layer's convolution operation, normalizing data across the entire mini-batch to address the issue of internal covariate shift.

In deep networks, convolution operation, nonlinearity, and batch normalization are typically applied in combination. Accordingly, this study sequentially connects convolution layers, activation layers, and batch normalization layers to construct a convolutional sub-network, as shown in the left diagram of Figure 3. This module extends the default parameters of *tensorflow.keras* application programming interface s (APIs) such as *Conv2D*, *ReLU*, and *BatchNormalization* by introducing an iteration parameter. By modifying this parameter, the depth of the convolutional sub-network can be controlled. This module is utilized by other sub-neural network modules or the overall network.

The transposed convolution layers and activation layers are sequentially connected to construct an upsampling sub-network, as shown in the middle diagram of Figure 3. Unlike methods such as nearest neighbor interpolation or max pooling, transposed convolution operations do not require predefined sampling methods. Instead, they derive weight and bias parameters through network learning, effectively reducing reliance on expert-based parameter selection. This module extends the default parameters of *tensorflow.keras* APIs like *Conv2DTranspose* and *ReLU* by introducing a list of upsampling factors. The upsampling factor list contains information on the factor values, execution count, and sequence for upsampling. In computation, the factor value is assigned to the stride as the scaling ratio for each upsampling operation. By increasing the values in the list, multiple upsampling operations can be achieved. It is worth noting that for the transposed convolution operation to achieve upsampling, the stride must be greater than 1.

By invoking the convolutional block, a residual mapping network is constructed. Adding a skip connection structure forms the residual sub-network, consistent with the architecture proposed by He in the 2015 ImageNet Large Scale Visual

Figure 3 | Modularized components of a deep network. From left to right: convolutional block in grayish blue, upsampling block in sky blue, and residual block in cream apricot, with APIs and blocks enclosed in solid and dashed rectangles, respectively.

Recognition Challenge (He *et al.* 2016), as shown in the right diagram of Figure 3. The residual mapping within this network is simulated by multiple calls to convolutional blocks. In the SRDRN network designed by Wang, the repetition count for this was set to 2 (Wang *et al.* 2021). Similarly, the functional module of this sub-network incorporates an iteration parameter to control the repetition count of the residual sub-network.

Architecture of the deep learning network

Using the TensorFlow machine learning platform with the Keras framework within the Python programming environment, we designed the Deep Residual Network for Precipitation Downscaling (DRN-PD), a deep learning architecture that incorporates inputs of two different resolutions to perform high-resolution precipitation downscaling. Unlike conventional CNN-based or U-Net downscaling architectures that process all inputs through a unified stream (Lin *et al.* 2023; F. Wang *et al.* 2023; Fu *et al.* 2024; González-Abad & Gutiérrez 2025), DRN-PD adopts a modular design that separates the processing of coarse-resolution atmospheric predictors and fine-resolution geospatial variables. The network is constructed using convolutional blocks, upsampling blocks, and residual blocks as sub-networks. By calling these sub-networks, a depth-adjustable overall network structure was built, as shown in Figure 4. This design enables efficient processing and integration of data at different scales, ensuring the model's effectiveness in handling the complexities of precipitation patterns.

As illustrated in Figure 4, the DRN-PD architecture integrates predictors at two distinct spatial resolutions through separate processing pathways. Input A consists of coarse-resolution meteorological variables from GCMs – RH, GPH, PSL, and TAS – which are relevant to precipitation dynamics. These variables are progressively upsampled via upsampling blocks, composed

Figure 4 | General architecture of DRN-PD. The diagram adopts the same color scheme and frame styles as in Figure 3.

of transposed convolution layers, to match the spatial resolution of the target precipitation output. Input B comprises high-resolution geospatial predictors, including annually updated LULC data and static domain masks. As these inputs are already aligned with the target resolution, they bypass the upsampling process and are directly fed into convolutional blocks for initial feature extraction without upsampling. The outputs from both pathways are concatenated and further processed through residual blocks, enabling hierarchical feature learning and integration. This modular design allows the network to effectively combine dynamic atmospheric conditions with temporally evolving surface characteristics and static spatial boundaries, ultimately producing high-resolution precipitation estimates.

A key strength of the architecture lies in its scalability and adaptability, allowing flexible adjustments to suit diverse regional contexts or research objectives: (1) Input A supports a range of coarse-resolution climate variables, such as RH, GPH, PSL, TAS, or alternatives like PW or zonal/meridional wind speeds (or combinations thereof). (2) The framework accommodates various GCM data sources, with upsampling blocks adjustable based on the resolution ratio between GCM data and the target output. (3) Input B flexibly incorporates static or dynamic geospatial variables (e.g., LULC, NDVI, or topography), with changes affecting only the number of input channels. (4) The network's depth, determined by the number of residual blocks, can be tailored to the problem's complexity and available training sample size.

This general DRN-PD architecture is instantiated for the YDM region, hereafter referred to as YDM-DRN-PD, with the detailed neural network structure illustrated in Figure 5. Input A consists of six meteorological variables: RH at 500 and 850 hPa, GPH at 500 and 850 hPa, PSL, and TAS, with a spatial resolution of 90×90 km. Input A undergoes three stages of upsampling, with upsampling factors – i.e., the stride parameters of *Conv2DTranspose* – set to 3, 2, and 3. This process transforms its pixel dimensions from 9×8 to 162×144 , refining the resolution by 18 times to achieve a tensor resolution of 5×5 km. Input B comprises land use/land cover (LULC) and domain masks with pixel dimensions of 162×144 , and physical variables are spatially resolved at 5×5 km. The output corresponds to CHIRPS daily precipitation, with pixel dimensions of 162×144 and a spatial resolution of 5×5 km. The neural network has a depth of 12 and consists of multiple layers with varying numbers of filters and a kernel size of 3×3 . The total number of parameters in the model is 1.6418 million, of which 1.6406 million are learnable. This architecture effectively captures and processes the complex spatial and temporal dynamics of precipitation in the YDM.

As shown in Figure 5, the network begins by separately processing Input A and Input B through dedicated sub-networks. Input A is passed through a sequence of upsampling blocks, each composed of transposed convolution layers with stride values of 3, 2, and 3, respectively. This progressively increases the spatial resolution to match that of the target output. In parallel, Input B is fed into convolutional blocks to extract spatial features from the high-resolution LULC and domain mask data. After these initial processing stages, the two feature maps are concatenated and passed through a sequence of three residual blocks connected in series, enabling progressive refinement of precipitation-relevant patterns. To enhance gradient flow and preserve global context, a global skip connection is applied across the entire residual stack, forming a unified residual structure. This design facilitates deep hierarchical learning while mitigating vanishing gradient issues. Finally, a convolutional layer denoted as *k3n1s1*—a 2D convolution with a 3×3 kernel, one output channel, and stride 1—is used to transform the learned features into the final precipitation output.

Training experiment

(1) Optimizer, loss function and metrics

The adaptive moment estimation (Adam) optimization algorithm, an improvement over traditional stochastic gradient descent, has been widely adopted in deep learning due to its advantages of high computational efficiency, low memory requirements, and suitability for large datasets or high-dimensional parameter spaces (Kingma & Ba 2014; Wang *et al.* 2021). In this study, the DRN-PD network optimizer utilized the Adam algorithm, with its learning rate parameter progressively reduced across four levels: $1e-3$, $1e-4$, $1e-5$, and $1e-6$, to refine the neural network toward optimal performance. For each learning rate, the network was trained for 20 to 40 epochs, ensuring sufficient refinement at each stage.

In neural network training, the objective function, commonly referred to as the loss function, plays a crucial role. Neural networks for precipitation downscaling are typically of a regression type. The mean square error (MSE) loss function is regarded as the preferred choice for regression networks under the theoretical framework of maximum likelihood estimation (Awasthi *et al.* 2021). Accordingly, this study employed MSE as the loss function, with root mean square error (RMSE) and mean absolute error (MAE) serving as evaluation metrics to assess network performance.

Figure 5 | Hierarchical architecture of YDM-DRN-PD. Visual encoding follows the same convention as Figures 3 and 4.

(2) Data preprocessing

Data from 1992 to 2014 was used to train the deep learning network. Prior to training, the raw data underwent preprocessing, including global normalization and data augmentation. Global normalization was implemented to eliminate the influence of differences in magnitude between variables. This study utilized standardization, whereby the dataset was normalized by subtracting the mean and dividing by the standard deviation. The mean and standard deviation were also employed in the subsequent inverse normalization process for post-processing simulation results.

Compared to non-rain periods, rainfall events are significantly less frequent, indicating noticeable sparsity in rainfall data. In other words, the effective data available for training was highly sparse. To address this, data augmentation techniques were introduced to expand the dataset, focusing solely on heavy rainfall events. All cell value of high-resolution CHIRPS precipitation were aggregated to form cumulative rainfall values, ranked by magnitude. The top 20% of rainfall data was selected as heavy rainfall events for augmentation (Wang *et al.* 2021). This study adopted five commonly used data augmentation methods: horizontal flipping, vertical flipping, rotation by 90°, 180°, and 270°. Each heavy rainfall data point underwent five rounds of augmentation, forming a dataset of the same size as the original data.

The framework for using original and augmented data in network training is presented in Figure 6. During network training, the ratios of the training subset to the validation subset were set at 0.8 for both the original and augmented datasets independently. Within the training subset, original data (Subset A) and augmented data (Subset C), as shown in Figure 6, were used in equal proportions. In contrast, the validation subset (Subset B) consisted exclusively of the original data. To balance computational efficiency and accuracy, mini-batches of size 64 were used during training instead of processing the entire dataset at once. After validation, the original and augmented datasets were combined and shuffled to ensure thorough mixing. This combined dataset was then used for an additional training phase of 10 epochs, enabling optimal utilization of the available data.

(3) Training implementation

The training and validation of the YDM-DRN-PD developed in this study were conducted on the Google Colab platform. The training process required high memory and computing power, primarily implemented using tensor processing units

Figure 6 | Dataset utilization strategy for YDM-DRN-PD training. Train subset A and C share the same shape, while test subset B and D also share the same shape.

(TPUs) v2-8 in high memory mode. The validation process required less memory and computing power. Depending on the availability of computing resources, TPUs or top-tier graphics processors used for deep learning, such as NVIDIA's Tesla P100/K80/T4, were utilized in combination with standard memory mode.

RESULTS

Training performance across seasons

The YDM region is characterized by a distinct four-season climate, with monsoon directions reversing between seasons, resulting in significant differences in rainfall patterns. To capture these seasonal variations, this study independently trained YDM-DRN-PD models for each season, generating an optimal model for each period. Learning curves, widely utilized in machine learning, serve as a visual method to depict the training process of neural network models, illustrating changes in accuracy and/or error over epochs (Goodfellow *et al.* 2016). The training errors of the YDM-DRN-PD models across the four seasons are visualized as learning curves in Figure 7, while the errors of the optimal models for each season are summarized in Table 2. In addition, to support broader comparison, several variant models and training experiments were documented in Table S1 of the Supplementary Material. These configurations represent intermediate versions of the DRN-PD framework explored during model development.

As shown in Figure 7, with an increasing number of training epochs, the training subset errors consistently decreased and gradually stabilized. However, the validation subset errors exhibited divergence during epochs 15–40 of the initial training phase. After decreasing the learning rate to $1e-4$, this divergence in the validation subset errors was resolved. When the learning rate was further reduced to $1e-5$, the models became notably stable. Although an additional adjustment of the learning rate to $1e-6$ resulted in slight error reductions, the magnitude of these reductions was minimal, indicating that further tuning of the learning rate would no longer enhance model accuracy. By epochs 100–110, the RMSE and MAE of both the training and validation subsets had stabilized. Consequently, the final iteration models were selected as the optimal models for their respective seasons: epoch 104 for spring/MAM and epoch 110 for summer/JJA, autumn/SON, and winter/DJF.

Based on Table 2, the error metrics across seasons demonstrate distinct patterns in both training and validation subsets. For the training subset, the RMSE ranged from 0.7480 in summer to 0.9783 in autumn, while the MAE remained relatively stable across all seasons, fluctuating between 0.4438 and 0.4557. In contrast, the validation subset exhibited more variation, with the RMSE peaking at 0.8331 in summer and reducing to 0.7584 in winter, and the MAE consistently lower than that of the training subset, ranging from 0.3272 to 0.4763. Although differences in RMSE and MAE values were observed between seasons, the overall error levels remained relatively consistent, particularly for the validation subset MAE, which demonstrated minimal seasonal variation (0.3272 to 0.4763). These findings underscore the robustness of the neural network structure in reliably adapting to seasonal changes in the YDM. Consequently, these seasonal-specific metrics played a critical role in determining the optimal models for each season.

Seasonal evaluation of precipitation

To evaluate the performance of the optimal models trained in the previous section, two experiments were designed:

(1) Overall error assessment

A random 20% subset of the original dataset was selected, and the optimal models were applied to reproduce rainfall data. RMSE, MAE, bias, Pearson's correlation coefficient (PCC), and Perkins' skill score (PSS) were calculated for each trial, and this process was repeated five times. The arithmetic mean of the results was then calculated separately for each optimal model, providing indicators of the overall error level across spring, summer, autumn, and winter.

(2) Heavy rainfall error assessment

To evaluate model performance under heavy rainfall conditions, the original dataset was sorted by total rainfall amount. The top 20% of the data, representing heavy rainfall events (consistent with the dataset used for data augmentation in the methodology section), was selected. The optimal models were then applied to reproduce rainfall data for this subset, with RMSE, MAE, bias, PCC, and PSS calculated as metrics of model error during heavy rainfall events.

The evaluation results, detailed in Table 3, reveal the effectiveness of the models in both general and extreme conditions. For overall error assessment, RMSE values ranged from 5.84 mm in winter to 11.28 mm in summer, while MAE values

Figure 7 | Learning curves for YDM-DRN-PD training: (a) Spring/MAM, (b) Summer/JJA, (c) Autumn/SOON, (d) Winter/DJF.

Table 2 | Error metrics for the optimal epochs/models of YDM-DRN-PD

Season	Training subset		Validation subset	
	RMSE	MAE	RMSE	MAE
Spring/MAM	0.8175	0.4438	0.8027	0.3920
Summer/JJA	0.7480	0.4557	0.8331	0.4763
Autumn/SOON	0.9783	0.4556	0.7662	0.3272
Winter/DJF	0.9177	0.4477	0.7584	0.3416

Table 3 | Error metrics for overall and heavy rainfall assessments using YDM-DRN-PD models

Season	Overall					Heavy rainfall conditions				
	RMSE (mm)	MAE (mm)	Bias (mm)	PCC	PSS	RMSE (mm)	MAE (mm)	Bias (mm)	PCC	PSS
Spring/MAM	7.99	4.59	-0.08	0.59	0.15	14.30	9.19	6.25	0.71	0.38
Summer/JJA	11.28	7.28	-0.55	0.65	0.23	16.18	10.95	5.70	0.75	0.46
Autumn/SON	7.42	3.50	-0.66	0.64	0.09	15.47	8.20	3.72	0.70	0.26
Winter/DJF	5.84	2.81	-0.35	0.62	0.09	10.72	5.99	3.67	0.72	0.24

ranged from 2.81 to 7.28 mm across seasons. Heavy rainfall errors exhibited higher variability, with RMSE ranging from 10.72 mm in winter to 16.18 mm in summer, and MAE spanning from 5.99 to 10.95 mm. These results indicate that the models achieve stable performance across seasons, with increased errors during heavy rainfall events reflecting the challenges posed by extreme conditions. In comparison with existing studies, the SRDRN model was reported to perform spatial downscaling of coarse-resolution rainfall data by a factor of 12, with error analysis for heavy rainfall events yielding RMSE and MAE values of 15.00 and 9.728 mm, respectively (Wang *et al.* 2021). The YDM-DRN-PD model developed in this study achieves comparable error levels, while performing a more aggressive downscaling – by a factor of 18—and incorporating eight physical environmental variables as input. A related model with a similar scaling objective is the Multi-Scale Residual Network proposed by Hsu *et al.* (2024), which achieved an even higher downscaling factor of 20× over Taiwan. Its reported optimal error metrics (MAE: 2.595 mm, RMSE: 5.542 mm) fall at the lower end of those observed for YDM-DRN-PD, demonstrating particularly strong performance in reconstructing general daily precipitation. However, it is worth noting that Hsu’s model employed a deeper architecture, with up to 22 cascaded convolutional layers, compared to a depth of 12 in our model. This comparison highlights the efficiency of the DRN-PD framework in achieving competitive accuracy with a more compact architecture, underscoring its enhanced capacity to generate fine-resolution precipitation estimates from coarse-scale predictors without compromising accuracy.

The bias metric in Table 3 provides further insight into model tendencies. For overall seasonal estimates, bias values are small and negative (e.g., -0.08 mm in spring, -0.66 mm in autumn), indicating a slight overestimation of precipitation compared to CHIRPS observations. In contrast, bias values under heavy rainfall conditions are consistently positive (e.g., 6.25 mm in spring, 5.70 mm in summer), suggesting a tendency to underestimate extreme precipitation events. This pattern reflects the smoothing effect commonly observed in deep learning models, which is partly attributable to the statistical nature of training objectives and the skewed distribution of rainfall intensity across space and time (Bhakare *et al.* 2025). The PCCs further support the model’s reliability. Across all seasons, PCC values under heavy rainfall conditions (ranging from 0.70 to 0.75) are higher than those for overall conditions (ranging from 0.59 to 0.65), indicating improved temporal agreement in capturing extreme events. To complement these deterministic metrics, we additionally incorporated PSS, a probabilistic indicator that evaluates the degree of overlap between observed and simulated precipitation distributions. Both PSS and PCC consistently identify summer as the season with the highest metric values. Notably, PSS values under heavy rainfall (e.g., 0.46 in summer, 0.38 in spring) substantially exceed those under overall conditions (e.g., 0.23 in summer, 0.15 in spring), suggesting that the model more effectively reproduces the statistical structure of precipitation during high-intensity episodes. This enhancement is likely attributable to the targeted data augmentation strategy applied during training, which improves the model’s sensitivity to extreme rainfall.

Seasonal assessment of spatial distribution

To assess the spatial performance of the YDM-DRN-PD model in simulating precipitation patterns, we extracted the maximum daily rainfall event for each season from the CHIRPS dataset over the period 1992–2014. The selected dates are: spring–2002-05-13, summer–2011-06-14, autumn–2007-09-18, and winter–2001-01-25. These representative events were chosen based on seasonal maxima in cumulative regional precipitation.

Figure 8 visualizes the spatial distribution of precipitation on these peak rainfall days, comparing CHIRPS observations with YDM-DRN-PD predictions. Overall, the model demonstrates strong capability in reproducing the spatial structure of

Figure 8 | Seasonal spatial distribution of CHIRPS and YDM-DRN-PD predicted precipitation on the maximum daily rainfall day.

observed precipitation, effectively identifying both the location and intensity of rainfall centers. The predicted magnitudes align well with CHIRPS, as indicated by the shared color scale, and the model successfully differentiates between regions of intense and weak rainfall. Closer inspection reveals structural differences between the two datasets. CHIRPS observations exhibit pronounced spatial discontinuities, with patchy rainfall and abrupt transitions between wet and dry grid cells – characteristics typical of convective systems. In contrast, the model outputs display smoother gradients, likely due to the convolutional architecture's tendency to aggregate local spatial information. This smoothing effect is particularly evident in the autumn case (2007-09-18), where CHIRPS shows numerous rain-free grid cells (white), while the model predicts widespread light rainfall (light green) across the same region. Minor checkerboard artifacts are also observed in the model outputs, especially in the autumn and winter panels. These faint striping patterns may result from transposed convolution operations during upsampling, which can introduce uneven spatial interpolation. Although subtle, such artifacts highlight a known limitation in certain deep learning architectures and suggest potential avenues for refinement.

Quantitative evaluation results are presented in Table 4, which reports cosine similarity (CS) and RMSE between CHIRPS and model predictions for each seasonal event. Metrics are stratified by precipitation intensity – slight ($1 \leq P < 50$ mm), moderate ($50 \leq P < 100$ mm), and heavy ($P \geq 100$ mm)—as well as overall seasonal performance. The model achieves high spatial similarity across seasons, particularly under moderate and heavy rainfall conditions. For example, in summer (2011-06-14), CS values reach 0.971 and 0.988 for moderate and heavy rainfall, respectively, with an overall CS of 0.968. Winter (2001-01-25) also performs well, with an overall CS of 0.960. Spring and autumn show slightly lower overall CS values (0.914 and 0.919), with autumn exhibiting the widest range – from 0.669 for slight rainfall to 0.953 for heavy rainfall – indicating greater difficulty in capturing fragmented precipitation during transitional seasons. RMSE values further support these findings. Summer yields the lowest overall RMSE (17.24 mm), reflecting high predictive accuracy, while autumn records the highest (37.99 mm), suggesting challenges in modeling spatial and intensity variability. RMSE tends to increase with precipitation magnitude, especially in spring and autumn, where heavy rainfall categories reach 59.59 and 53.81 mm, respectively. Winter shows a relatively balanced RMSE profile across precipitation ranges (21.15–25.92 mm), indicating consistent model performance under stable meteorological conditions.

Error distribution characteristics are further illustrated in Figure 9, which presents violin plots of absolute and relative errors for each season and precipitation category. The left column shows absolute errors, which increase with precipitation intensity across all seasons. The highest quartile ranges and medians are observed in the heavy rainfall category ($P \geq 100$ mm). In contrast, the right column displays relative errors, which decrease as precipitation increases, suggesting improved model accuracy under heavier rainfall conditions. This trend implies that slight rainfall ($1 \leq P < 50$ mm) is more difficult to simulate precisely, likely due to its sporadic and localized nature. Seasonal variability is also evident in the error distributions. For heavy rainfall events (green violins), spring and autumn exhibit broader spreads and higher medians, consistent with transitional monsoon dynamics and increased spatial heterogeneity. Summer and winter, by comparison, show narrower distributions and lower median errors, reflecting more stable atmospheric regimes and enhanced model consistency. Most violin plots resemble inverted tadpole shapes with extended tails, indicating occasional large deviations between YDM-DRN-PD predictions and CHIRPS observations. Notably, the blue violins representing slight rainfall ($1 \leq P < 50$ mm) in subplots (f) and (h) exhibit relatively broad distributions along the y-axis, with large relative error quartiles. In other words, the error values are evenly dispersed across the full range, without a distinct concentration around the

Table 4 | Spatial similarity and RMSE between CHIRPS and YDM-DRN-PD predictions on the maximum rainfall day

Metrics	Precipitation range	Spring/MAM: 2002-05-13	Summer/JJA: 2011-06-14	Autumn/SON: 2007-09-18	Winter/DJF: 2001-01-25
CS	$1 \leq P < 50$	0.911	0.894	0.669	0.562
	$50 \leq P < 100$	0.926	0.971	0.843	0.965
	$P \geq 100$	0.928	0.988	0.953	0.977
	Overall	0.914	0.968	0.919	0.960
RMSE	$1 \leq P < 50$	17.20	14.38	22.08	24.95
	$50 \leq P < 100$	27.19	17.16	41.62	21.15
	$P \geq 100$	59.59	26.38	53.81	25.92
	Overall	33.35	17.24	37.99	24.15

Figure 9 | Violin plots of relative and absolute errors between CHIRPS and YDM-DRN-PD predictions on the maximum rainfall day.

median. These characteristics reflect greater uncertainty in simulating low-intensity rainfall, likely due to its sporadic and spatially fragmented nature. Despite these outliers, the overall distribution patterns confirm that the YDM-DRN-PD model maintains robust predictive accuracy across a wide range of precipitation intensities and seasonal conditions.

In summary, the combined visual and quantitative analyses in [Figure 8](#) and [9](#) and [Table 4](#) demonstrate that the YDM-DRN-PD model performs reliably in capturing the spatial distribution of precipitation. While minor artifacts and discrepancies exist – particularly under light rainfall and transitional seasonal regimes – the model exhibits strong spatial adaptability and predictive fidelity, especially under moderate to heavy rainfall conditions.

DISCUSSION

Predictors and framework

The selection of predictors is a pivotal aspect of precipitation downscaling research, and this study introduces a dual-resolution framework that integrates coarse-resolution atmospheric variables alongside fine-resolution land use data to simulate daily precipitation. This approach offers two key advantages: enhanced interpretability of rainfall simulation mechanisms and the flexibility to explore interactions between regional climate dynamics and anthropogenic surface modifications. Urban agglomerations, such as the YDM, characterized by intense human activity and rapid land transformation, present unique challenges that this methodology is specifically designed to address. Environmental factors – including land use change, vegetation cover, topography, and urbanization – can significantly alter surface energy balance, moisture fluxes, and convective dynamics, thereby reshaping precipitation patterns and introducing spatial heterogeneity that coarse-resolution models often fail to capture. For instance, impervious surfaces enhance sensible heat flux and reduce evapotranspiration, urban aerosol accumulation increases cloud condensation nuclei and modifies cloud microphysics, and urban-induced wind fields can disrupt the organization and movement of rain-bearing clouds. These mechanisms underscore the importance of incorporating land use data into downscaling frameworks.

While deep learning for precipitation downscaling has gained traction, the combined use of meteorological predictors and land use data remains underexplored. Two prevailing strategies dominate deep learning applications in precipitation downscaling. The first utilizes the super-resolution paradigm, reconstructing coarse precipitation grids into finer resolutions without directly incorporating ancillary variables. Studies such as [F. Wang et al. \(2023\)](#) and [Jin et al. \(2025\)](#) have advanced this approach, achieving refinement factors of $6\times$ to $12\times$. While effective in enhancing spatial resolution, this method often overlooks critical drivers of precipitation such as land use, vegetation indices, orographic features, and urban heat islands ([Sha et al. 2020](#); [Hsu et al. 2024](#); [Manco et al. 2025](#)). Moreover, its limited physical interpretability constrains its applicability for regional climate impact assessments. The second strategy uses rainfall-related climate variables as inputs to simulate precipitation fields ([Jin et al. 2023](#); [Lin et al. 2023](#)). For example, [Fu et al. \(2024\)](#) incorporated atmospheric predictors like GPH and PW, achieving improved precipitation representation. These studies enhance the physical relevance of deep learning models by linking meteorological inputs to rainfall outcomes ([Pan et al. 2019](#); [Sun & Lan 2021](#); [González-Abad & Gutiérrez 2025](#)). However, the absence of land-use information in these models restricts their ability to represent how climate circulation and anthropogenic surface changes jointly influence precipitation behavior. The framework proposed in this study bridges these approaches, leveraging atmospheric variables for regional climate dynamics while integrating high-resolution land use data for fine-scale spatial precision. This integration enables more physically grounded and spatially precise precipitation simulations, particularly in complex urban environments.

Despite these strengths, several limitations warrant further investigation. First, although data augmentation was applied to improve model sensitivity to heavy rainfall, bias metrics reveal a tendency toward smoothed forecasts – underestimating extreme rainfall peaks while overestimating weak or no rainfall. This reflects a common challenge in deep learning models trained on skewed precipitation distributions. Future work could explore hybrid architectures that combine regression and classification ([F. Wang et al. 2023](#)), or implement hybrid loss functions that explicitly weight extreme rainfall events ([Bhakare et al. 2025](#)). Integrating statistical downscaling techniques may also offer complementary benefits, though preliminary results (e.g., multi-task sparse structure learning coupling with BCSD) suggest that such coupling requires careful calibration to avoid performance degradation ([Vandal et al. 2019](#)). Second, while the inclusion of land use data is a key innovation, current high-quality LULC datasets are typically updated on an annual basis and fail to capture intra-annual surface variations, particularly in regions with pronounced seasonal vegetation cycles. This limitation highlights the need for temporally dynamic, high-resolution predictors such as NDVI, land surface temperature, or monthly LULC composites. The modular design of the DRN-PD architecture supports flexible integration of such variables, extending its applicability beyond urban regions to mountainous, arid, or coastal landscapes ([Zhu et al. 2025](#)). Third, the model's interpretability remains an open challenge. While the dual-resolution design improves physical relevance, the internal mechanisms of

deep neural networks are still difficult to trace. Future research could incorporate explainable AI (XAI) techniques – such as layer-wise relevance propagation or feature attribution – to better understand how specific predictors influence rainfall outputs across space and time. Taken together, these limitations point to promising directions for future work. By refining model architecture, expanding dynamic predictor sets, and enhancing interpretability, the DRN-PD framework can evolve into a robust tool for regional climate adaptation and hydrological planning.

Model performance and training strategies

The YDM-DRN-PD model demonstrates exceptional performance in reproducing heavy rainfall events, which remains a critical challenge in precipitation modeling. A key factor in this success is the training strategy, wherein the dataset was augmented with synthetic heavy rainfall scenarios, causing such data to constitute 60% of the entire training subset. This design ensured robust representation of extreme patterns, thereby enhancing the model's sensitivity to high-intensity events. The resulting RMSE and MAE values for these scenarios, ranging from 10.72 to 16.18 mm and 5.99 to 10.95 mm, respectively, compare favorably with established benchmarks (Wang *et al.* 2021). This finding aligns with literature highlighting that deep learning models trained on augmented datasets exhibit superior performance in extreme climate scenarios (F. Wang *et al.* 2023; González-Abad & Gutiérrez 2025).

Despite this strength, the model's performance under slight or low-intensity rainfall conditions is limited, as indicated by broader error distributions and higher relative errors. This difficulty in capturing sporadic drizzle events stems from fundamental challenges in atmospheric modeling. Firstly, the inherently fragmented and fine-scale nature of drizzle is poorly represented by conventional deep learning models, which tend to produce spatially smooth or blurry forecasts that average out these details (Ravuri *et al.* 2021). Secondly, slight precipitation is often governed by local microphysical processes that have weaker correlations with the large-scale atmospheric predictors typically used as model inputs, making it a difficult signal for the network to learn (McGovern *et al.* 2023). This results in the model struggling to capture the stochastic nature of such events, leading to lower predictive skill (Rasp & Lerch 2018).

Furthermore, architectural limitations manifest as spatial artifacts in the model's output. A general smoothing effect, resulting from the convolutional architecture's tendency to aggregate local features, can obscure the fine-scale discontinuities characteristic of convective rainfall (Fu *et al.* 2024). More pronounced checkerboard artifacts, observed particularly during autumn and winter, underscore the well-documented limitations of using transposed convolutions for upsampling (Manco *et al.* 2025). Future work should focus on mitigating these issues. Incorporating stochastic components or refining predictors could improve low-intensity precipitation modeling, while architectural adjustments – such as adopting hybrid sub-pixel convolutions or GAN-based frameworks – could enhance spatial fidelity by reducing artifacts.

Broader implications and future directions

The DRN-PD architecture is not limited to the YDM region; its modular design and dual-resolution pathway make it well-suited for diverse terrains and climatic regimes. The hybrid framework supports a range of applications, including regional climate analysis, urban flood management, and water resource planning (Hsu *et al.* 2024; Bhakare *et al.* 2025). It can incorporate CMIP6 projections under various Shared Socioeconomic Pathway (SSP) scenarios to enable high-resolution downscaling for future-oriented climate adaptation strategies. For example, precipitation projections for June 2050 under SSP245 and SSP585 are presented in Figures S4 and S5 of the Supplementary Material, driven by BCC-CSM2-MR predictors and business-as-usual LULC data. These outputs can inform hydrological simulation, guide blue-green-gray infrastructure design, and support climate-resilient planning (P. Wang *et al.* 2023; Dong *et al.* 2025). To enhance robustness under non-stationary conditions, ensemble modeling, uncertainty quantification, and multi-variable downscaling warrant further exploration, alongside improvements in LULC temporal resolution and rainfall predictor interpretability (González-Abad & Gutiérrez 2025).

CONCLUSIONS

This study presents the DRN-PD, a modular deep residual neural network for daily precipitation downscaling. By integrating atmospheric predictors and high-resolution land use data, the framework both the underrepresentation of coarse-resolution GCM outputs in regional climate analysis and the absence of land use information of existing downscaling methods. Applied to the YDM region, the model demonstrates strong generalization across seasons and rainfall regimes.

Seasonal training and targeted data augmentation strategies yielded stable performance, with validation RMSE ranging from 0.7584 to 0.8331 and MAE from 0.3272 to 0.4763. Under general conditions, the model achieved RMSE values between 5.84 mm (winter) and 11.28 mm (summer), while under heavy rainfall, RMSE increased to 10.72–16.18 mm. Spatial evaluations on seasonal peak rainfall days confirmed high similarity with CHIRPS observations (cosine similarity >0.96 in summer and winter), and violin plots revealed robust predictive accuracy under moderate to heavy rainfall. Compared to existing deep learning models, DRN-PD achieves competitive accuracy with a more compact architecture and a higher down-scaling factor (18×), while explicitly incorporating land use information.

Nonetheless, the model exhibits several limitations: weak skill scores under overall assessments – primarily due to light or no rainfall conditions – smoothing effects that dampen extreme precipitation peaks, and checkerboard artifacts in the spatial distribution. These findings highlight opportunities for improvement through hybrid training skill, ensemble modeling, and alternative upsampling strategies.

The DRN-PD framework is readily extensible to other regions and future climate scenarios, owing to its modular design and customizable predictor sets. Illustrative projections for June 2050 under SSP245 and SSP585 demonstrate its potential to support hydrological modeling and climate-resilient infrastructure planning. As such, DRN-PD offers a scalable and adaptable solution for high-resolution precipitation modeling, with practical implications for flood risk assessment, water resource management, and urban climate adaptation.

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DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

All relevant data are available from an online repository or repositories. The population and GDP used in Figure 2 were collected from the Statistical Yearbooks for all included cities and the World Bank. They are available on Zenodo with a DOI of <https://10.5281/zenodo.4059316> and are free to use and distribute under the CC BY 4.0 license. The original boundary of the Yangtze Delta Megalopolis is courtesy of OpenStreetMap. Terrain tiles used as background in Figure 1 are courtesy of Stamen Design. Meteorological variables from the CSM2-MR model are courtesy of the Beijing Climate Center and Google Cloud (<https://console.cloud.google.com/marketplace/product/noaa-public/cmip6>). Land cover images from 1992 to 2014 are courtesy of the European Space Agency (<https://www.esa-landcover-cci.org>). CHIRPS data are courtesy of UC Santa Barbara (<https://www.chc.ucsb.edu/data/chirps>).

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare there is no conflict.

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